

The role of photovoltaics for the European Green Deal and the recovery plan

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ABSTRACT

The European Green Deal was published at the end of 2019 and represents EU's biggest action to reach climate neutrality. The European Recovery Fund was presented in July 2020 as a response to the COVID-19 crisis. This study looks at the role that photovoltaics could play to support the successful implementation of these initiatives, in particular in regard to the increased climate ambition. The European Commission proposal of September 2020 (55% emission reduction in 2030 compared to 1990) and the European Parliament proposal that followed soon after (–60%), have changed the level of greenhouse gas reduction ambitions. Energy system modelling shows that achieving the updated targets will require large quantities of renewables deployed at an unprecedented pace. Over the past 10 years solar PV has achieved the technological and market maturity to spearhead EU efforts to reach the energy and climate targets. The paper looks at future projections of solar PV deployment, also considering ongoing sectorial policies (e.g. the EU hydrogen strategy, the building renovation wave) and overarching aims for system integration and a just transition.

1. Introduction

In April 2009, the first European Union Renewable Energy Directive (RED) went into force. Between then and the end of 2019, the total capacity of grid-connected solar photovoltaic (PV) systems in the European Union (EU 28) had increased more than 10-fold from 11.3 GWp at the end of 2008 to over 134 GWp at the end of 2019 [1]. What will the 2020 to 2030 decade bring?

In December 2018, the recast Renewable Energy Directive (RED II) set a target of 32% share of renewable energy and at least 40% greenhouse gas (GHG) emission reduction by 2030 compared to the 1990 levels [2].

During the 25th session of the Conference of the Parties (COP25) in December 2019, the European Commission president Ursula von der Leyen presented the European Green Deal [3] which includes a set of policy initiatives to reach climate-neutrality and make the EU economy sustainable. The European Green Deal targets climate neutrality by 2050, and aims to support companies to become world leaders in clean products and technologies, as well as to ensure a just and inclusive transition [4].

In order to set a legal framework for this, a proposal for the European Climate Law was published in March 2020 [5]. In mid-September 2020,

the European Commission proposed to raise the 2030 climate targets to 55% GHG reduction by 20230 [6]. The accompanying Impact Assessment [7] demonstrates that such an increase in the climate ambition is realistic and economically feasible. Naturally, such an increased GHG reduction target will require a revision of the renewable energy and energy efficiency policies. According to the Impact Assessment [7], the 55% target will require a share of renewable energy around 38.5% by 2030. In October 2020, in a vote on the EU Climate Law, the European Parliament (EP) raised the ambition even further, calling for a GHG reduction of 60% in 2030 and highlighted the necessity for an interim 2040 target [8]. In December 2020, the European Council representing the EU's Member States finally endorsed the new binding EU target for a net domestic reduction in GHG emissions of at least 55% by 2030.

Proposals on how to finance the Green Deal were presented in January 2020 and intended to mobilize EUR 1 trillion of sustainable investments over the next decade [9]. Moreover, as a response to the economic slowdown due to the COVID-19 crisis, the European Council agreed on a EUR 672.5 billion recovery and resilience facility on 21 July 2020 [10]. This fund aims to support EU's sustainable and resilient recovery, by creating jobs and repairing the immediate damage caused by the COVID-19 pandemic whilst supporting the EU's green and digital priorities. EU Member States will prepare national recovery and resilience plans with their individual reform and investment agendas for the

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Nomenclature			
AC	alternating current	GW	gigawatt
ALLBNK	scenario based on MIX and further intensified fuel mandates for the aviation and maritime sectors	H ₂	hydrogen
BSL	base line scenario	LTS	long-term strategy
COP	conference of parties	MIX	combined approach of REG and CPRICE scenarios
CPRICE	carbon-pricing based scenario	MS	EU Member States
CRiT	coal regions in transition	NECP	National Energy and Climate Plans
CTP	common transport policy	NZEB	nearly zero-energy buildings
DC	direct current	PRIMES	price-induced market equilibrium system [energy system model]
EC	European Commission	PV	photovoltaic
EE	Energy efficiency	RED	Renewable Energy Directive
EP	European Parliament	REG	regulatory-based measures scenario
EU	European Union	RES	renewable energy sources
EUR	Euro	R&I	research and innovation
GHG	greenhouse gas	TWh	terawatt-hour
		Wp	Watt peak (nominal power of a PV module under standard test conditions)

years 2021–2023. Each recovery and resilience plan has to include a minimum of 37% of expenditure earmarked for actions to combat climate change.¹ Accordingly, it is expected that the annual EU budget set in the multiannual financial framework and the recovery and resilience facility will dedicate significant amounts to clean energy systems and spur private investments in the sector. The renovation wave of EU's building stock can further support the solar sector [11].

This article analyses the status and recent developments in the EU's PV sector. More ambitious energy models exist than the PRIMES scenarios used for EU's policy-making and the legislative process. Some of these have considered scenarios with 100% renewable power or even 100% renewable energy by 2050 [12–14]. Similarly there are several country-specific analyses for high levels of renewables. A recently published study from the International Energy Agency and the French transmission system operator RTE looked at the conditions and requirements for a French power system with 50–100% by 2060 [15]. However, this article just considers the PRIMES energy model projections and future scenarios of PV deployment for the EU with a short- and long-term horizon (2030 and 2050, respectively). The reason for this choice is that in the European policy framework, only these model scenarios have been politically endorsed so far.

2. State of play

2.1. Solar PV power capacity installations in EU

At the end of 2019, the total installed PV power capacity in the EU (27) and the United Kingdom had surpassed 134 GWp (Fig. 1) [1]. Residential, commercial and industrial rooftop installations again increased their market share and accounted for more than 60% of the cumulative installed capacity by the end of 2019 [17]. These 81 GWp on rooftops is roughly 15% of the already identified rooftop potential in the EU (27) and the United Kingdom [18].

The annual PV market for new PV systems in the EU and Great Britain had declined for six years before the trend was reversed in 2018. The annual market increase continued in 2019 when the EU (27) and the United Kingdom added about 16.5 GWp of new PV power capacity (Fig. 2). Spain (4.5 GWp), Germany (3.9 GWp) and the Netherlands (2.4 GWp) were the leading three countries [19,20]. For the first time Poland was in the top-5 countries with a new installed PV capacity of about 800 MWp. Another four countries added more than 500 MWp, namely

Belgium, France, Hungary and Italy.

Market maturity and technological advancements of photovoltaics contributed to their recent increased deployment rates. Such progress has made PV one of the most cost-effective power generation technologies [21,22]. In the last few years, an increasing number of EU Member States have introduced competitive auction schemes for solar power. This development enables tendering large PV capacities at once and fosters competition that reduces costs. Ensuring equality of opportunity encourages a larger number of potential investors to participate in such auctions and increases competition. This has resulted in a series of successful auction calls in terms of both allocated power capacities and prices that encourage the procurement of successive calls.

As mentioned in the introduction, the recent policy developments [6, 8] have risen the bar compared to the recast Renewable Energy Directive (RED II) [2] and call for accelerated reduction of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in the EU. Solar PV is one of the main technologies that are readily available to achieve these targets.

2.2. Costs trends for solar PV and investments in the EU

From a global perspective, the cost of solar PV systems has decreased rapidly over the last decade. Solar module prices further decreased in 2020 with some analysts attributing this to a combination of increasing production in China and the decreased energy demand due to the COVID-19 outbreak that pushed prices down [23]. Indeed, between January and December 2020, the cost of bifacial modules in EU has decreased by 15.4%, while the mainstream modules became cheaper by 12%. Prices reached a minimum in mid-October 2020, but then took an upward direction as a combination of the sustained COVID-19 crisis, challenges in the module transportation and supply chain, and increased demand. Fig. 3 shows module prices by technology in the EU spot market.²

Bifacial: with bifacial cells; All black: black back sheets & frames, 290–390 Wp; High efficiency: ≥ 320 Wp with PERC, HJT, n-type or back-contact cells; Mainstream: multicrystalline silicon, 275–315 Wp; Low cost: factory seconds, insolvency goods, used or low-output crystalline modules, products with limited or no warranty.

As a result of the fall in prices, in 2020, the levelized cost of electricity (LCOE) of solar PV has become for the first time lower than that of onshore wind in Europe [25]. Despite that there were concerns that the COVID pandemic could lead to a decline in investments into PV.

¹ Details available in the dedicated Q&A section: https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/qanda_20_1659.

² Prices refer to the spot market (without VAT) and are not end-customer prices. More information: www.pvXchange.com.

Fig. 1. Grid-connected PV capacity in EU (27) and the United Kingdom, including pre-COVID estimates for 2020 (2020e) [1].

Fig. 2. Annual PV capacity additions in EU (27) and the United Kingdom, including pre-COVID estimates for 2020 [1].

Fig. 3. EU spot market PV module prices by technology Sep. 2019–Oct. 2020 [24].

However, contrary to the investment decrease forecasted by the IEA, based on the global PV market in the first half of 2020, investments in solar energy actually increased by 12% to USD 148.6 billion (\approx EUR 125 billion [26,27]).

3. The role of photovoltaics in future EU strategies

3.1. Solar PV in the European Green Deal and the Climate Law

The European Commission (EC), presented its strategy for increased climate ambition in the Communication of mid-September 2020 as part of the Green Deal package and the recovery and resilience facility [6]. In this policy document, the EC commits to climate neutrality by 2050 and raises the climate ambition in the short-term horizon aiming for 55% GHG reductions by 2030. The Communication prioritizes the creation of an international *level playing field* for all renewable energy sources (RES) –including PV– and the relevant raw materials. The document refers to the European Climate Law proposal and, by extension, the detailed *Impact Assessment* that accompanies it (parts 1 and 2). The *Impact Assessment* provides future projections for the European energy system via an energy model simulation that uses the PRIMES model [28,29]. PRIMES provides projections for demand/supply, emissions, costs and investments.

Several scenarios were reviewed to explore possible future pathways for the EU (27)'s energy systems. The baseline scenario (BSL) aligns with the 2030 energy and climate framework and leads to -46% GHG emissions by 2030 (-59% in 2050). Additional scenarios explore possible pathways to achieve -55% by 2030 i.e. the target set by the EC Communication [6]. These “policy scenarios” include the case of increased carbon price accompanied by RES deployment and measures to promote energy efficiency (EE) and clean transport (CPRICE scenarios), the case of a balanced intensification of RES/EE/clean transport and carbon pricing policies (MIX scenario), and a case of intensified energy and transport policies with moderate carbon pricing (REG scenario). Moreover, the ALLBNK scenario explores even higher levels of climate ambition (-58% GHG by 2030), also considering measures for the aviation and navigation sectors.³

As far as solar PV deployment is concerned, each scenario provides projections for 2030 and 2050.⁴ Table 1 summarises these projections

Table 1

Energy model projections for solar PV capacity deployment in EU 27 and associated GHG emissions reductions.

Scenario	2030 GHG reduction ^a	Solar PV generation capacity (GWac)			2030 elec. generation (TWh)	2030 PV share in elec. gener.
		2018 [22]	2030	2050		
BSL	-46.9%	104	311	465	3116	12%
CPRICE	-55.0%		363	1065	3170 ^b	14%
MIX	-55.0%		370	1060	3120	14%
REG	-55.0%		363	1040	3120	14%
ALLBNK	-57.9%		374	1060	3130	14%

Source: Stepping up Europe's 2030 climate ambition – *Impact Assessment* [7].

^a Values compared to 1990 and include the net LULUCF sink.

^b Except from the BSL, values of total electricity production are approximations derived from in part 2/2 of [7].

³ The impact assessment also considers variants of the BSL and the policy scenarios that result in relatively lower reduction (-50% GHG). Since both EC and EP consider such levels of ambition insufficient, this paper did not analyse these variants.

⁴ Values refer to solar energy in general, however concentrated solar power is expected to also play a minor role that is not considered here.

for each scenario and presents them next to the projected GHG emission reduction. The results show that the EC proposal to raise the climate ambition to -55% GHG emissions will require at least 52–59 GWac of additional solar PV generation capacity until 2030 compared to the -46% GHG case (covered by the BSL scenario). This difference is reflected on the increased electricity generation from solar PV (Table 1, column 4) that needs to be installed to raise reductions from 46.9% to at least 55%. In terms of average annual installations, these updated targets would require at least 21–22 GWac of solar PV capacities installed every year in the EU. As shown in Fig. 2, this range is slightly higher the historic peak values of PV deployment (e.g. 18.8 GWp in 2011 [30]).

If the EP proposal to raise further the 2030 climate target to reduce GHG by 60% were to have been accepted, additional PV capacities would be needed, although the *Impact Assessment* does not analyse such a scenario. However, an approximate evaluation is possible by looking at the ALLBNK scenario and at the 2050 figures of the BSL scenario. ALLBNK achieves 57.9% reductions in 2030 and this includes the installation of 374 GWac of PV. However, the ALLBNK applies the GHG target by including mitigation measures for international aviation and maritime navigation. In short, it achieves higher reductions through a specific pathway that mitigates emissions in sectors not powered by RES. The BSL reaches -59% GHG by 2050 and this involves the installation of 465 GWac of solar PV. By applying a linear interpolation between the simulation outputs of BSL (2050), the policy scenarios (CPRICE, MIX, REG - 2030) and the ALLBNK (2030), it appears that 60% GHG emission reductions in 2030 would require the installation of 415–490 GWac of PV, depending on the scenario. Obviously, pathways that prioritise electrification across all sectors tend towards the higher value of this range and converge to nearly 500 GWac of PV in the EU. In the case of pathways that take additional mitigation measures to RES deployment (e.g. decarbonisation of aviation and maritime navigation) the required PV deployment is relatively lower and closer to 415 GWac in 2030.

Accordingly, the projected additions of PV capacity between 2018 and 2030 are in the 311–386 GWac range. This is equivalent to an average annual installation rate of 26–32 GWac of PV in the EU, which is 25–50% higher than that of the -55% GHG case. This shows that in case the EP proposal prevails, significantly higher amounts of PV installation would be needed even under the conservative case.

3.2. The envisaged role of PV in the 2018 EU long-term strategy (LTS)

In 2018, the European Commission presented a long-term strategic vision for a climate neutral economy [31], together with an in-depth analysis of pathways to realise this [32]. The commitment of the new European Commission for increased climate ambition [6] has superseded the LTS analyses to a large extent. Still, the projections of the LTS energy modelling exercise are included here to allow comparisons. In that way, it will become clear what raising the climate bar means for the solar sector and to what extent efforts to deploy PV need to be intensified.

The LTS presented nine different scenarios for the EU (then including the UK) to achieve decarbonisation targets by 2050. A GHG emission reduction of 46% is projected in all scenarios for 2030. This is slightly higher than the 40% reduction target of RED II [2], but significantly lower than the recent proposals of the European Commission (55%) and the European Parliament (60%). The envisaged solar PV capacity under the LTS (-46%) is in the 320.5–330 GWac range, which is higher by 8–10.5% compared to the capacity needed (303.6 GW) to achieve the -40% GHG emission target in RED II [33].

A recent analysis of the LTS [34] data showed that in order to achieve -55% GHG reductions, 364–484 GWac of PV is needed, depending on the scenario. The LTS was released in the Brexit transition period in 2018 and any comparison needs to take UK installations into account. Estimates for PV installations in UK by 2030 range between approximately 20 and 40 GWac for the low and high case, respectively [35]. According to our analysis of the LTS results [34] and excluding UK, it

appears that 344–444 GWac of PV are required in EU 27 to reach –55% GHG emissions. The 2020 *Impact Assessment* [7] scenarios are in close agreement to the lower bound of the accelerated LTS scenarios and show a tighter range. The upper limit of the LTS range (444 GWac) is significantly higher (+18.7%) than the *Impact Assessment* values presented in [Table 1](#) (363–374 GWac). This reflects specific scenarios developed at the time that anticipate increased role for power-to-X, deep energy efficiency measures, and a highly circular economy.

3.3. National energy and climate plans (NECP)

At the end of 2019, the EU Member States (MS) submitted 10-year integrated national energy and climate plans (NECP) for the period from 2021 to 2030. NECPs outline the strategy the MS intend to address the climate and energy targets [36]. This includes RES deployment, energy efficiency measures, GHG emission reductions, interconnections, research and innovation (R&I).⁵

Concerning PV, the NECP present the planned capacity deployment of the MS to reach the targets of the RED II by 2030. Each country provided a range of capacity depending on the level of ambition. [Table 2](#) presents country-level figures for both levels of ambition and the current (end of 2019) installed capacity.

In the low case, the total PV capacity in 2030 in EU (27) is approximately 260 GWp, while for the high-ambition it exceeds 341 GWp. Compared to the *Impact Assessment* [7], the gap between the NECPs PV capacity and the capacity needed to reach the –55% GHG target is 140–150 GWp, while in the high case it narrows to 60–70 GWp. This shows

Table 2
Installed capacities in EU (27) for 2019 and NECP estimates for 2030 – low and high cases.

Country	Capacity 2019 [GWp]	Capacity 2030 (low) [GWp]	Capacity 2030 (high) [GWp]
Austria	1.70	3.00	12.00
Belgium	4.86	7.66	11.00
Bulgaria	1.07	2.90	2.90
Croatia	0.06	0.77	0.77
Cyprus	0.15	0.80	0.80
Czechia	2.22	3.98	3.98
Denmark	1.40	7.84	7.84
Estonia	0.12	0.42	0.42
Finland	0.20	1.20	1.20
France	9.90	25.00	25.00
Germany	49.18	71.88	97.92
Greece	2.91	8.00	8.00
Hungary	1.60	6.00	6.00
Ireland	0.05	1.25	1.50
Italy	20.87	27.00	51.12
Latvia	0.01	0.50	0.50
Lithuania	0.11	1.53	1.53
Luxembourg	0.19	0.7	1.11
Malta	0.15	0.26	0.26
Netherlands	6.81	18.00	36.00
Poland	1.31	7.30	7.30
Portugal	0.80	9.00	9.00
Romania	1.40	5.89	5.89
Slovakia	0.57	1.20	1.20
Slovenia	0.30	1.65	1.65
Spain	10.97	44.00	44.00
Sweden	0.69	2.50	2.50
Total EU (27)	119.6	260.23	341.39

Source: [36].

⁵ Detailed information and the final NECP of the EU countries are available at: https://ec.europa.eu/energy/topics/energy-strategy/national-energy-climate-plans_en.

the need to rapidly update the NECP deployment plans and the necessary capacity additions to reach the upgraded target of the Green Deal that result in –55% GHG emissions. To note the wide range between the NECP low and high cases exceed 80 GWp. This wide range increases uncertainty and risks getting off track with the Green deal's objectives.

4. Discussion

The previous section looked at the role of PV under current EU policies and strategies in various future pathways through the various scenarios. This section presents and analyses some key assumptions and provides a better understanding of the factors that shape the future role of photovoltaics.

4.1. Electricity demand and supply

The extent of deployment of renewables is intrinsically linked to the growth of electricity consumption associated with electrification of the transport, heating and cooling and industrial sectors. The common transport policy strategy presented in the *Impact Assessment* [7] anticipates a moderate increase of electricity generation in the EU for the next decade. Gross electricity generation in EU (27) increases in the BSL scenario from 2902 TWh (2015) to 3116 TWh (2030). Notably, this increase by 7.4% is almost uniform among scenarios as the policy scenarios and the ALLBNK anticipate similar increase levels.

However, in the 2050 projections the situation alters: while the BSL scenario anticipates an additional 17% increase that results in 3650 TWh of gross electricity generation in 2050, the policy scenarios anticipate a two-fold increase (>100%) i.e. generation exceeding 6000 TWh or even reaching 7000 TWh (CPRICE) [7]. This difference is due to electrification of demand, notably, in transport and shows that climate neutrality in 2050 will bring at least twice the current electricity generation under all scenarios. These trends are even more pronounced in the 100% renewable electricity and 100% renewable energy scenarios being proposed for Europe that can be found in various articles [14–16,37]. All highlight the importance and value of PV to the energy transition. In March 2020, six EU Member States sent a joint letter to the European Commission requesting the inclusion of a 100% RES scenario (2050) in its climate mitigation pathways [37], indicating increasing openness to such concepts.

For the 2030 timeframe, a critical issue will be the availability of the various technologies to achieve the targets, pointing to a reliance on wind and solar PV, which have already achieved high levels of technological and market maturities. At the same time, the integration of this additional solar PV capacity in the existing power grid will require a bundle of measures ranging from investments in transmission and distribution networks, national and regional interconnections, demand and supply side management to centralised and decentralised storage systems.

A recurring question is the availability of land for the required PV capacity. Under conservative assumptions, ground mounted PV system in the EU have a technical potential to generate more than 2850 TWh of electricity annually [14]. In addition, there is the rooftop potential, which does not use productive land and can provide electricity close to the point of consumption, which reduces the need for long-distance transmission. A high-resolution geospatial assessment of the rooftop solar photovoltaic potential in the EU quantified the availability of rooftop area and estimated that the technical potential for PV systems on existing buildings in EU (27) is at 640 TWh annually, 460 TWh of which could already be generated at economically competitive terms [38]. This corresponds to a total PV power capacity of about 560 and 400 GWp, respectively.

4.2. Green hydrogen as driver for renewables

The future role of solar PV will also depend on the degree on which

green hydrogen production will move on. Currently hydrogen is still 97% based on fossil fuels [39]. A clean hydrogen economy can only be realised with the use of carbon-free electricity to produce and supply green hydrogen. The Green Deal's Communication related to the hydrogen strategy for a climate-neutral Europe [40] sets out a vision of installing in the first phase at least 6 GW of green hydrogen electrolyzers by 2024 and –in a second phase– at least 40 GW of RES-powered electrolyzers by 2030. The full-time operation of this level of electrolyser capacity would require the equivalent electricity output of 256 TWh. The policy scenarios of the Impact Assessment [7] anticipate an electrolyser capacity between 37 and 66 GW by 2035 [7]. The comparison of this to the figures provided in the hydrogen strategy reveals that the underlying assumptions in the Impact Assessment [7] may be conservative. The EU industry has announced an even more ambitious plan to develop 80 GW of electrolyzers by 2030 in both EU Member States (40 GW) and neighbouring countries (40 GW) [41]. In mid-2020, 1.5–2.3 GW of new green hydrogen production projects were under construction or announced, and an additional 22 GW were in the pipeline [40].

A recent study shows that the current annual EU hydrogen production of 9.75 Mt if produced by electrolysis would require at least 73 GW of fully-utilized electrolyzers. Such electrolyser capacity would need an additional 468 TWh of electricity⁶ [39]. Moreover, the electrification of the electrolyser capacities envisaged in the hydrogen strategy is expected to require the connection of 80–120 GWac of wind energy and solar PV [41]. In case technological progress, innovation, and implementation projects of green hydrogen production advance in a higher pace than expected, additional RES capacities will be needed. Accordingly, a faster progress in deployment rates or the installation of capacities larger than that anticipated in the Impact Assessment [7] will lead to increased needs for solar PV generation and a proportionate increase of the PV capacity installations.

4.3. Photovoltaic module market

The energy system model simulation underpinning the projections in the Impact Assessment [7] and the LTS analysis [32] report projections of solar PV capacity as alternating current (AC) capacity to be comparable to the other power generation plants. Indeed Eurostat official statistics record the power capacity at the connection point to the grid. However, for the PV industry, the direct current (DC) capacity is important because it determines the PV module production and installation volumes.

In the recent years, the rapidly falling prices of solar modules have encouraged additional oversizing of the (DC) solar arrays relative to the inverter (AC) rating. A system with a high DC-to-AC ratio (also known as inverter loading ratio) generates additional quantities of AC electricity early and late in the day. When the DC generation is higher than the rated power of the inverter (e.g. at noon), the excess part of the produced energy is curtailed, a concept known as solar clipping. Overall, the system obtains a net benefit in terms of energy output. Typical utility-scale solar PV systems apply an inverter load ratio (ILR) of 1.2–1.3 in order to optimise system performance [42]. In the past, PV plants were designed with relatively low ILR (≈ 1.1). Presently, the incremental cost of installing more (DC) PV capacity has become low compared to the system fixed costs [43]. For this reason, systems with relatively higher ILR become increasingly common. As an example the 2019 median IRL of utility-scale PV systems in Florida was 1.5 [44].

This development is particularly important as far as PV module manufacturing is concerned. In case high ILRs become the norm, the required PV module (DC) volumes can be significantly higher than the values presented in Section 3, and 550–650 GWP may be needed for the various policy scenario pathways. Obviously, such volumes would have

significant implications for PV industry and its value chains.

4.4. Building renovation wave

The transformation of the Energy Performance of Building Directive recast with the concept of Nearly Zero-Energy Buildings (NZEBs) in national legislation can create an additional momentum for PV systems on roofs [45]. Making mandatory the installation of renewable energy systems in new buildings is currently under discussion at municipal and regional level in the EU. Considering that approximately 1.6 million new residential buildings were constructed in 2016 [46] in the EU (27), an average 4 kW PV on each building would add more than 6 GWp per year or another 60 GWp until 2030. In case the annual number of housing completions rebounds to that of the 2000–2009 (2.2–2.8 million annually), new buildings could host up 11 GWp of solar PV, annually. The Green Deal also includes the Renovation Wave strategy [47] that refers to the 85% of the EU building stock (>220 million buildings) built before 2001 and in need of refurbishment by 2050. Currently, the renovation rate is approximately 1% per year (≈ 2.2 million annually) with only one-fifth ($\approx 440,000$ buildings) of the cases including significant improve of energy efficiency. The Green Deal aims to double these rates by 2030. Overall, the Renovation Wave strategy offers an additional opportunity for the development of residential solar PV systems.

4.5. Employment, job creation and just transition

The realisation of the rooftop potential on existing and new buildings could create a significant number of local jobs. Employment for rooftop PV installations considerably depends on local regulations and building codes and in general is higher than that for large systems. However, considering the job numbers provided by the USA Solar Census 2018 for large scale systems as a benchmark, the installation and maintenance of new rooftop systems could add 100,000 to 190,000 new jobs by 2030 [48]. In addition such a development would also have a positive impact for jobs related to battery storage and related sectors. Strong synergies with the transition in the transport sector with road vehicles can be expected. These numbers are in line with studies that recognise the importance of solar PV sector as a job creator and refer to direct net employment [49–51].

A realisation of the Green Deal has far-reaching consequences for the EU industrial sector. It will have a direct impact on those European regions where coal and lignite are still mined (42 regions across 12 EU countries and the United Kingdom) and used in thermal power plants. Coal mining is still a significant economic activity but its phase out is crucial to achieve the GHG emission reduction targets. A social acceptable alternative employment has to be found for the estimated 240,000 people working in the sector (180,000 in the coal and lignite mining and 60,000 in coal and lignite power plants) [52].

The technical potential for solar photovoltaic electricity generation in the EU's Coal Regions in Transition (CRiT) was analysed and resulted in a potential of 650 GWp (mines and surrounding areas) in these regions [43,52]. The development of PV systems on these areas would create minimum land use conflicts and would allow integrated brown-field redevelopment solutions [53]. If large-scale PV systems would be build flanking the retirement of the coal plants in these regions over the next decade, over 225,000 construction jobs per year would be created, while the O&M sector could employ about 56,000 jobs in 2030. Nonetheless, even if the installation of solar photovoltaic electricity generation systems will provide new jobs, not everybody currently working in the mining sector will be able to transfer to one of these new jobs. Therefore, additional flanking measures for a just energy transition have to be put in place.

The economic viability of solar PV in the CRiTs depends on various parameters such as cost of finance, electricity market maturity, supportive mechanisms and others that exceed the scope of this study. Obviously, a crucial factor is the solar resource potential available in

⁶ Assuming an electrolyser efficiency value 48kWh/kgH₂ that is not current state of the art, but a likely development by 2030.

each region [52]. A regional analysis shows that for the case of mines the expected productivity of ground mounted PV ranges between 11.4% and 19.6% in EU 27 with an average value of 13.5%. Concerning surrounding areas of mines, the average value is even higher at 14.4% (11.1%–18.6%), while for rooftop installations slightly lower at 13.0% (11.0%–18.1%). These figures show that CRiT include some prime locations and areas with advantageous solar potential that could be cost efficient. Even in the less favourable locations, the falling prices of PV makes their majority cost-competitive.

5. Outlook

The European Green Deal aims to put the European Union on a pathway to reach at least 55% of GHG reduction by 2030, and requires bold action to accelerate the decarbonisation of our energy supply. The demand for clean power production could increase even more than anticipated if a tipping point for accelerated electrification were to be reached. The consequence is that proven technologies like wind and solar photovoltaics will have to bridge the gap. Accelerating the deployment of solar photovoltaics is a “no regrets” choice as it has one of the lowest electricity generation costs.

The Green Deal and the COVID-19 recovery and resilience facility offer a unique opportunity to accelerate this development and streamline European and national efforts. Low risk financing in all Member States as well as a redesign of the electricity market regulations are amongst the crucial measures. The proposed renovation wave of public and private buildings, a green hydrogen industry and the electrification of the transport sector can both revitalise the economy and contribute to achieving the GHG reduction targets.

A massive expansion of the European PV system market requires resilient and sustainable supply chain, supported by research and innovation. New cell and module manufacturing capacities in the EU can be a part of this. Together with the downstream PV system businesses, they offer a significant job creation potential. The just transition dimension can be further strengthened by ensuring a significant share of decentralised PV to provide local jobs and ensure citizen participation.

Last but not least, an analysis and comparison of the worldwide efforts to cut GHG emissions and to reach the target of no more than 1.5 °C at the end of the century need further attention. The recent study looking at the impacts of Green New Deal Energy Plans worldwide (100% wind, water and solar supply and storage) on grid stability, costs, jobs, health, and climate in over 140 countries is a first step, which needs to be continued [54].

Credit author statement

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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